

**POLYTECHNIQUE
MONTREAL**

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MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF NEWLY DEVELOPED ABRADABLE MATERIALS FOR ADDITIVE MANUFACTURING

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A large commercial airplane is shown from a low-angle, front-facing perspective, flying over a city. The plane is white with two engines mounted on the wings. The city below is a mix of modern and older buildings, with a hazy sky in the background. The runway is visible in the foreground.

ICAO environmental objectives for 2050

- 1- Reduce CO₂ emissions by 75%
- 2- Reduce noise level by 65%

INTRODUCTION

Thermoset composite

Abradable composite materials

- Reduce clearance
- Limit aerodynamic losses
- Blade tip sealing
- Preferential coating wear
- Decrease fuel consumption

Manual application [4]

Abradable coating [3]

Leap-1A turbofan [2]

2. safran-group.com, 2016
3. Legrand et al., 2012
4. <http://www.afiklmem.com>

ADDITIVE MANUFACTURING OF ABRADABLE MICROSCAFFOLD

Jean-François Chauvette, PhD

6-axis robot with a half engine fan case

Non-planar DIW of abrasion-resistant micro-scaffold network using multinozzle printhead on a FFF of a curved HTRP sandwich panel

ABRADABLE MATERIAL FORMULATIONS

DIW of abrasible micro-scaffold [5]

ABRADABLE FORMULATIONS

Materials

- i) Epoxy resin
- ii) Glass microspheres (GM)
- iii) Fumed silica (FS)

DIW MICROSCAFFOLD

0GM.12FS

5GM.10FS

10GM.8FS

$\rho = 1.279 \text{ g/cm}^3$

$\rho = 0.598 \text{ g/cm}^3$

$\rho = 0.792 \text{ g/cm}^3$

Lee Lee Hia,
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David Brzeski,
Msc

Fail micro-scaffold -
DIW of commercial
abrasible product

[5] D Brzeski, IL Hia, JF Chauvette, etc., Additive Manufacturing, 47, 2021, 102245.

MECHANICAL TEST I: SHORE D

Molded 0GM12FS abrasible coating

Shore D durometer

- Increasing of GM loading decreases in Shore D hardness
- Higher GM loading leads to higher porosity, thus reducing hardness

MECHANICAL TEST II: ADHESION TEST

Pull off adhesion test [6]

Pull off adhesion test on abrasible coating

- The pull out strength increases with GM loading
- Without GM, the adhesion of the abrasible coating is poor on the aluminium substrate
- Benchmark with highest GM loading (~23wt%) has poor adhesion on the substrate

MECHANICAL TEST III: ABRADABILITY TEST

(a) Schematic of abrasability test rig with three titanium blades attach on rotating disk. Images taken from the (b) camera and (c) thermal camera during the abrasability test.

MECHANICAL TEST III: ABRADABILITY TEST

- Overall, the abrasability of 3 new abrasible materials are comparable with Benchmark
- There is no material adhesion on the TA6V blades, smooth cutting tracks observed thus the abrasibles are being removed easily
- Dust formation and pores clogging might affect acoustic properties

Top view of (a-c) 3D printed abrasibles micro-scaffolds and (d-f) coatings showing the tracks after being abraded by TA6V blades. Dust traces generated are found in the pores of microscaffolds.

MECHANICAL TEST III: ABRADABILITY TEST

- The higher penetration depth of abrasible coating compared to microscaffold could be due to the higher temperature recorded which also softens the materials, thus more materials being abraded
- The highest penetration depth found in 10GM8FS microscaffold could be due to the high porosity and fragility of abrasible materials, thus the internal structures could be easily compacted during the blade scratching rather than being removed
- Overall, the DIW microscaffold made of 0GM12FS and 5GM10FS were having great abrasibility which is very similar to the Benchmark

SUMMARY

- New DIW abrasable materials have been developed and they are successfully printed into microscalfold network
- Their mechanical properties (i.e. Shore D, adhesion and abrasability tests) were evaluated as compared to the commercial abrasable product
- Impact of fume silica on the hardness is insignificant compared to glass microspheres. Increasing of glass microsphere increase the Shore D hardness of abrasable materials
- Higher GM loadings lead to higher pull out strength and also the adhesion on the aluminium substrate
- Two abrasable materials (0GM12FS and 5GM10FS) showed better abrasability as compared to 10GM8FS material

Thank You Team Objective 4!

